

DESIGNING A MODEL TO EXPLAIN THE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES OF UNIVERSITIES BASED ON A SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP APPROACH

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Abstract

Nowadays, the development of social entrepreneurship is considered as a social and philanthropic mission, and one of the ways to solve some problems and social harms. Entrepreneurship has had a positive and future impact on many different activities of countries; On the other hand, it can cause economic development and create job opportunities, and on the other hand, it can improve the social and cultural condition of the society. The present study aimed to design a model to explain the social responsibilities of universities based on the approach of social entrepreneurship in the universities of Khuzestan province. The present research method was a developmental-exploratory study. The statistical population of the research included 30 university professors using purposive sampling and the brainstorming method (interview with experts) and it continued until it reached theoretical saturation. In this research, it has been used the Delphi method based on the identification of the central phenomenon, causal conditions, contextual and intervening factors, strategies and consequences and the relationship between them. Examining the data obtained in the first stage of open coding, 36 concepts about social entrepreneurship and 48 concepts about social responsibility were obtained.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Social Entrepreneurship, Social Responsibility.

INTRODUCTION

Social responsibility in universities, as a dynamic organization, implies the creation of a link between the knowledge produced in various contexts and local, national and global needs, and includes a wide range of actions and processes that are used to respond to the needs of the environment. They are implemented in appropriate and effective ways. To respond to this, universities should establish a close relationship between their inherent functions and reconsider their roles related to the environment to solve the complex problems of the 21st century (Farhadi Rad et al., 2020, 34). Therefore, addressing the category of social responsibility is fruitful not only for industrial and service organizations, but also for universities and higher education centers and will help to build a committed society (Habibi et al., 2016, 128).

According to the definition by Vasilescu et al. (2010), globalization, knowledge society, innovation, development of technologies, growth based on market pressures and environmental

degradation have had important effects on the mission of universities, organization and profile, mode of operation and distribution of higher education. All these trends in development have expanded the footprint of the university in the society and have created growing social expectations for increasing the importance of the responsibility of the universities towards diverse groups of stakeholders. According to Valais (2008), the social responsibility of the university is the policy of ethical quality in the activities of the university community during the responsible management for the educational, cognitive, work and environmental effects of the university, which is in active dialogue with the society to promote sustainable human development; It occurs in four stages: commitment, self-diagnosis, adaptation and accountability (Baradaran Haghiri et al., 2019, 6).

Griffin and Barney define social responsibility as follows: social responsibility is a set of duties and obligations that the organization must perform in order to care for and help the society in which it operates. Sooter and Graff also defined the social responsibility of the company as follows: the commitment, the task of the management to do things that protect and promote the welfare of the society and the interests of the company. Wentzel (1991) considers social responsibility to respect the rights of others, individual competition and moral development and has directly related it to learning. He considers social responsibility in having a sense of decision-making, creativity and independent thinking, which is the opposite of obedience and domineering behavior. Castka & Balzarova (2007) consider social responsibility as a continuous commitment to behave in an ethical manner by improving the quality of life of individuals and their families, as well as improving society on a wider scale (Mojibi & Nabavi, 2014, 34).

On the other hand, currently, educational authorities also consider social entrepreneurship as a new field to offer to students (Arab et al., 2013, 66). On the other hand, the necessity of academic entrepreneurship and the creation of an entrepreneurial university as one of the vital strategic and key tools of higher education to face these changes and pressures has become clear by issues such as the increasing pressure on the government and the Ministry of Science, Research and Technology and the reduction of the government budget in recent years, the increase in the number of graduates, increasing unemployment and the employment crisis of young people, especially educated ones, change in the expectations of university applicants, competition, changing needs of the market, responsibility and accountability in front of society, revolution of quality and productivity, change in knowledge and the necessity of knowledge management and its commercialization, the necessity of transformation in traditional education and the trend towards new education and applied research, the necessity of using technologies and other things that have caused transformation in the mission, role and functions of the university. Also, in recent years, innovation has been emphasized in all aspects of the university, but in the latest approach, social entrepreneurship has also been proposed as an integral part of the entrepreneurial university. This approach of the entrepreneurial university has been formed in response to concerns about the weakening of the direction of the universality of higher education by the profit-seeking market, and in the traditional concept of the entrepreneurial university, the entrepreneurial activities of the universities is interpreted in terms of economic benefits, but recently more attention has been drawn to the social value of

such scientific entrepreneurship. Universities that are supposed to be on the path of continuous excellence and serve the development and progress of their communities are called social entrepreneurial universities in the new definitions (Nadali Pourpelki et al., 2019, 270). With this approach, the study of social entrepreneurship in the country's educational organizations such as universities should be given more attention. Accordingly, the main goal of the current research is to design a model to explain the social responsibilities of universities with a social entrepreneurship approach. Therefore, in this regard, the research seeks to answer general questions including the following:

1. What are the dimensions of social entrepreneurship in the universities of Khuzestan province?
2. What are the main components of social entrepreneurship in the universities of Khuzestan province?
3. What are the dimensions of social responsibility in the universities of Khuzestan province?
4. What are the main components of social responsibility in the universities of Khuzestan province?

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Social Responsibility

Responsibility or accountability refers to the sense of being responsible (Holdorf & Greenwald, 2018, 116). Being responsible means increasing a person's resistance to the situation in order to follow internal requirements instead of following external pressures (Pogh et al., 2019, 341). Carroll (1979), considers corporate social responsibility as a set of duties and social obligations of the company, including optional, economic, legal, and ethical responsibilities.

Economic responsibility: It is a type of economic responsibility that includes creating investment returns and profitability for owners and shareholders, fair payment to employees, creating new resources, promoting technology, innovation and creating new services and products.

Legal responsibility: Legal responsibility includes compliance with local, national, and international laws and regulations.

Ethical responsibility: Ethical responsibility is to fulfill other social expectations as unwritten rules such as avoiding social damage, respecting people's rights, etc. This type of responsibility is basically rooted in the consideration of human rights.

Voluntary responsibility: This responsibility takes place with the tendency of economic enterprises to participate in social affairs that are not economical, legal and binding. This responsibility is the main standard of social responsibility of a company that goes beyond expectations and is done to participate in government and social activities (Rahchamani and Kavousi, 2015, 70).

Social Responsibility of the University

The social responsibility of the university refers to the fact that in the higher education system of most countries, a series of career and professional activities and programs have been developed as university activities in line with the social responsibility of the university. Regarding the definition of social responsibility of the university, Riser considers it as a policy of the moral quality of the performance of the university community (students, professors and executive staff), which is carried out through the responsible management of educational affairs, human resources and environmental effects resulting from the academic activities in an interactive dialogue with society to promote sustainable human development (Tetrevova, 2010). In other words, academic social responsibility means providing educational services and spreading knowledge in an ethical way, which is actually the same as competent management, respect and commitment to society (Viscoes et al., 2014, 146).

Entrepreneur University

Entrepreneurship refers to the process of starting the production of an idea for a product or realizing a service through risk management. Entrepreneurship is innovation and an entrepreneur create a new combination; therefore, an entrepreneur is an innovator. According to Schumpeter, two concepts of entrepreneurship and innovation are almost inseparable (Yurtkorua, 2014, 835). Academic entrepreneurship is an attempt to increase the interests, influence and prestige of an individual or an institution, which should be done by developing and marketing research ideas or by integrating new roles and resources in the existing organizational framework and creating new models for researchers' studies. (Zali et al., 2013, 92). An entrepreneurial university means a university in which all the activities of the members such as education, research, etc. are managed, administered and executed in such a way that the university is considered as an economic institution or quasi-corporation; That is, the orientation of these activities should be in the direction of profitability and gaining competitive economic advantages (Dabic et al., 2015, 169)..

Social Entrepreneurship

According to the definition of Gregory Days (1998), social entrepreneurship includes the activities that a social entrepreneur performs and includes the concept of creating value, innovation and being the agent of change, searching to discover opportunities and resourcefulness; It covers the following seven components: social entrepreneurs who are agents of change in the social sector, the mission of creating and maintaining social values (and not only private values), recognizing and pursuing new opportunities to achieve the mission, being in a continuous process of innovation, adaptation and learning, bold activity regardless of the limitations of available resources, creating a sense of responsibility towards institutions that are effective in creating results and creating quasi-market mechanisms (Habibi et al., 2020, 64).

University Social Entrepreneurship

According to researchers, social entrepreneurship in the university means the production and construction of social capital, which is the basis for the comprehensive development of society,

including economic, political, scientific and cultural dimensions; In other words, finding the legitimacy of the university by fulfilling social responsibilities. Teaching this type of entrepreneurship in the university creates the spirit of self-sufficiency, creativity, empathy and logical thinking and provides the basis for the progress and academic success of students (Nadali Pourpelaki et al., 2019, 271).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Habibi et al. (2020) investigated the impact of social entrepreneurship orientation on social innovation, the results of this research showed that social entrepreneurship orientation has a positive and significant effect on social innovation, as well as social innovation on innovation in products and innovation in services.

Farhadi Rad et al. (2019) identified and analyzed the social responsibilities of the university in a research. According to the results, 20 central categories of social responsibilities of the university were identified, and the logic of Carroll's model was used to categorize them. Also, the single-sample T-test showed that the status of the social responsibility components of the university in the overall scale of 2.92 was higher than the hypothetical average of the research (2.5) and the T-value was 15.69; They were in a favorable and satisfactory condition.

Nadali Pourpelki et al. (2019) conducted a research with the aim of explaining the background conditions for the development of social entrepreneurship in universities and higher education institutions of Iran. The results showed that factors such as potential talents with the sub-categories of personal qualifications and group qualifications, public policies with the sub-categories of formalization and procedures of entrepreneurs and material and spiritual investment with the sub-category of social capitals and financial capitals were identified as background factors for the development of social entrepreneurship in higher education.

Fazeli et al. (2019) identified the challenges and social strategic activities of social entrepreneurship. The findings of this research showed that social entrepreneurs need to know the challenges and strategic actions in the surrounding environment. Recognizing social challenges makes them able to recognize an important part of their obstacles and introduce them to the environment and society around them and act with cooperation and consensus to solve them.

Zare and Safari Dashtaki (2019), in a research, designed and explained a paradigm model of social entrepreneurship with the approach of empowering women heads of households. The results showed that empowering policies as a central phenomenon and in interaction with other factors lead to the formation of social entrepreneurship and capacity building, physical and mental strengthening and supporting laws are very effective in the formation of enabling policies; In the end, this attitude becomes the basis for the emergence of the social entrepreneurship phenomenon.

In a research, Shokohi et al. (2017) identified and prioritized strategies for the development of social entrepreneurship. The results showed that political, institutional and legal factors are the most effective factors on the development of social entrepreneurship from the experts' point of

view. Women are the head of the household and the factor of business facilities is ranked second. Also, out of the 37 determined strategies, the strategies of insurance for women heads of the household, support and services for product marketing, and providing employment facilities to the women of the household, have been ranked first to third, respectively.

Pedro Torres and Mário Augusto (2020), in an article entitled “Digitalization, Social Entrepreneurship and National Welfare”, examined the impact of digitalization and social entrepreneurship on national welfare. The results show that if the country has an adequate education system, proper governance and a benevolent financial system, digitization can benefit the national welfare. Digitalization can use these conditions to promote national welfare. This study also contributes to the entrepreneurship literature by clarifying the role of social entrepreneurship.

Nazha Gali et al. (2020), in a research, investigate the effect of the trend towards social entrepreneurship, the behavioral measure of social entrepreneurship of the organization on the social and financial performance of a sample of Austrian companies. Despite the growth of research interests in social entrepreneurship, the field remains fragmented and this has led to calls for a careful examination of the implications of social entrepreneurship for companies. Using stakeholder theory and hybrid organization, they presented the hypothesis that social performance mediates the relationship between the tendency towards social entrepreneurship and financial performance. Analyzing a sample of 1,156 companies, they found that the relationship between social entrepreneurship and financial performance is partially mediated by social performance, and the direct effect was negative.

Shari et al. (2019), in a research entitled “The Role of Social Responsibility of Malaysian Universities in Educating Competent Citizens in Malaysia”, they found that the university has been very effective in educating good and worthy citizens in Malaysia with its facilities and services that it can provide to the society.

Fawad Latif (2017), in a research entitled development and trust building of a customer-centric scale for measuring university social responsibility stated that the social responsibility of the university has seven basic dimensions: 1- operational responsibilities 2- research and development responsibilities 3- customer-oriented responsibilities 4- legal responsibilities. These four responsibilities were classified. The fifth responsibility was moral responsibilities, the sixth responsibility was voluntary responsibilities, and the seventh responsibility was humanitarian responsibilities.

METHOD

The research method was a developmental-exploratory study. In this research, the Delphi method has been used based on the identification of the central phenomenon, causal conditions, contextual and intervening factors, strategies and consequences and the relationship between them. The statistical population of the research included 30 university professors using purposive sampling and the brainstorming method (interview with experts) and it continued until it reached theoretical saturation.

FINDINGS

Open Coding: Open coding consists of two stages: In the first stage, each component is given a title and a label. This title, so-called "code", should be indicative of the content of the data, so that the researcher and reader, by observing this title, can understand the meaning of the sentences to a large extent. The second stage is focused coding, which consists of using the most meaningful or abundant primary codes to sift and reduce a large volume of data. In this stage of coding, the researcher puts similar and common codes in the form of a single category by determining and arranging the codes with concepts. The naming of the categories is based on the researcher's understanding of the topic and the common content of the open codes (concepts); In this research, 48 concepts were extracted, which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The initial stage of open coding of the qualitative data for the social responsibility model of the university

Row	Code	Concepts	Categories
1	F1	Applying the continuous process of innovation, adaptation and learning	adaptation and learning
2	F2	Agents of change in the social sector	Agents of change in the social sector
3	F3	Identification and stubborn encouragement of new opportunities	Identification of new opportunities
4	F4	Accepting the mission to create and survive of social value	survive of social value
5	F5	Necessary processes and structures with cultural compatibility in mind	adaptation and learning
6	F6	Applying a written evaluation system based on future changes	Applying a written evaluation system
7	F7	Focus on strategic positions	Focus on strategic positions
8	F8	Evaluation of existing capabilities and needs assessment of university missions in the future	Evaluation of existing capabilities
9	F9	Identification and recruitment of capable forces	Identification and recruitment of capable forces
10	F10	Economic and organizational incentives to motivate the development of social entrepreneurship	development of social entrepreneurship
11	F11	Serious and fearless action through available resources	Serious and fearless action through available resources
12	F12	Providing an ambitious sense of accountability to institutions and resulting outcomes	accountability to institutions and resulting outcomes
13	F13	Creating a platform for transformational leadership and reforming processes and structures	reforming processes and structures
14	F14	Applying the written evaluation system and paying attention to the future educational needs of the society	attention to the future educational needs of the society
15	F15	Evaluation of existing capabilities and potentials	Evaluation of existing capabilities

16	F16	Attention to education based on future needs and innovation	Attention to the future educational needs of society
17	F17	Assessing needs and using all capacities to provide them	Assessing needs and using all capacities
18	F18	Applying new management methods in coordination and compatibility between industry and university	The connection between industry and university
19	F19	Informing people of the effectiveness and importance of their role in accepting the responsibility of creating change in the social sector	The effectiveness of people in creating change in the social sector
20	F20	Identifying new opportunities, teaching and learning principles	Identifying new opportunities
21	F21	Discovering people's talents and skills instead of educational credentialism	Identification and recruitment of capable forces
22	F22	Welcoming new ideas and opinions	Identifying new opportunities
23	F23	Knowing critical and strategic situations in the organization	Focus on strategic positions
24	F24	Identifying the capabilities of people and creating a sense of responsibility in them	Identification and recruitment of capable forces
25	F25	Using factors such as organizational incentives	reward system
26	F26	Creating incentive mechanisms to encourage people to accept social responsibility	Development of social entrepreneurship
27	F27	Need assessment of training courses related to the field of entrepreneurship	Attention to the future educational needs of society
28	F28	Improving processes and structures by assigning and equipping practical workshops	Modifying processes and structures
29	F29	Assessing the current situation and formulating educational programs according to existing capacities and future needs	Identifying new opportunities
30	F30	Forming entrepreneurial groups and creating the necessary infrastructure	Identification and recruitment of capable forces
31	F31	Appropriate needs assessment and selection of people with related capabilities	Identification and recruitment of capable forces
32	F32	Preference for resources within the organization and for additional skills that are not available in the organization	Serious and fearless action through available resources
33	F33	Attention to the role of new technologies that can be used	Using up-to-date technology
34	F34	Providing an ambitious sense of accountability to institutions and resulting outcomes and serious and fearless action through available resources	Serious and fearless action through available resources
35	F35	Identification and stubborn encouragement of new opportunities and agents of change in the social sector	Identifying new opportunities
36	F36	Attention to human potential and available resources and attention to the necessary structures for the optimal use	Identification and recruitment of capable forces

37	F37	Explaining the role of universities in identifying the needs of society and the ways to meet them	Attention to the future educational needs of society
38	F38	Optimal allocation of resources and efficient human resources	Identification and recruitment of capable forces
39	F39	University and industry connection	University and industry connection
40	F40	Educational and hardware processes and structures	Using up-to-date technology
41	F41	Assessment of existing capabilities and social needs	Development of social entrepreneurship
42	F42	Effective and efficient management of resources with a regional and sector perspective	Development of social entrepreneurship
43	F43	Serious and fearless action through available resources	Serious and fearless action through available resources
44	F44	Accepting the mission to create and survive social value	Development of social entrepreneurship
45	F45	Evaluating the existing conditions and capabilities and drawing the optimal conditions with the priority of strategic needs	Focus on strategic positions
46	F46	Appropriate management based on the attitude of local conditions	Development of social entrepreneurship
47	F47	Creating inter-organizational communication and coordination of all organizations in line with social responsibilities	Development of social entrepreneurship
48	F48	The university's ability to adapt to the conditions in the market and industry and the needs of society	Development of social entrepreneurship

Also, examining the data obtained in the first stage of open coding, 36 concepts related to social entrepreneurship were obtained, which are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The first stage of social entrepreneurship open data coding

Row	Code	Concepts	Categories
1	E1	The university rector's belief in entrepreneurship and innovation	Management attitude to entrepreneurship
2	E2	Encouraging and persuading professors to carry out entrepreneurial activities by the university rector	Management attitude to entrepreneurship
3	E3	Appointment of vice presidents with entrepreneurial and innovative attitude and thinking by the university rector	meritocracy and competency-based selection
4	E4	Holding national and annual conferences and meetings by university entrepreneurship centers	Scientific conference
5	E5	Establishing permanent secretariats of scientific conferences on the subject of entrepreneurship and innovation at the university level	Entrepreneurial structures
6	E6	Responsiveness to society	Social consequences
7	E7	Responding to social demand	Social consequences
8	E8	Responding to the labor market	Economic consequences
9	E9	Employment opportunities for students	Employment of students

10	E10	Creating competition between universities	Competition of universities
11	E11	Editing and preparing a joint publication between the university, industry and entrepreneurs	Common research activity
12	E12	The research centers in the university	Research activity
13	E13	The university-affiliated research centers	Research activity
14	E14	Reduction of unemployed graduates	Reduce unemployment
15	E15	Approving research projects with the subject of entrepreneurship, technology and innovation	Entrepreneurship research projects
16	E16	Inclusion of academic entrepreneurship goals in the statement and missions of the university	The mission of entrepreneurship
17	E17	Hiring specialist staff in the research and development department	Recruitment
18	E18	Identifying the talents and entrepreneurial abilities of professors	Talent management
19	E19	Promoting the culture of entrepreneurship and innovation in the university	Entrepreneurial culture
20	E20	Formation of university entrepreneurship corridors	entrepreneurship corridors
21	E21	Forming a committee and specialized group of entrepreneurship and innovation in the university	Entrepreneurial structure
22	E22	University membership in professional and international entrepreneurship institutions and associations	Extra-university communication
23	E23	Holding development courses for faculty members with a focus on entrepreneurship and technology	Professional development of entrepreneurship
24	E24	Applying the spirit of innovation and entrepreneurship in university management and planning	structural reform
25	E25	Organizational excellence of the university	Organizational Excellence
26	E26	Inviting local entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university	Interaction with the national environment
27	E27	Inviting national entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university	Interaction with the national environment
28	E28	Inviting international entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university	Interaction with the transnational environment
29	E29	Communication with work environments and labor market	Interaction with the labor market
30	E30	Creating commitment and attachment to the category of entrepreneurship among faculty members	Entrepreneurial culture
31	E31	The university rector's commitment to the development of entrepreneurship	Entrepreneurial culture
32	E32	Creating an entrepreneurial atmosphere	Organizational Culture
33	E33	Communicating with justice and establishing rights between university and industry	Sustainable interaction with the industry

34	E34	Strengthening collective identity among academic agents	Participatory Culture
35	E35	Encouraging and encouraging teamwork among academic staff	Participatory Culture
36	E36	Creating a sense of belonging to entrepreneurship in employees and professors	Organizational Culture

After performing the operation of the initial stage of open coding, in the second stage of open coding, similar and common concepts and categories were integrated through constant comparative analysis of data. In this way, relying on the most meaningful and abundant concepts and primary categories, sifting and reducing a large volume of data was done. At this stage, while referring to similar concepts and categories and comparing them with each other, trying to identify overlapping concepts and categories and by determining and sorting them, common concepts and categories in the form of one concept and We put a single category. At this stage, while referring to similar concepts and categories and comparing them with each other, we tried to identify overlapping concepts and categories and by determining and arranging them, we put common concepts and categories in the form of a single concept and category. Based on this, the volume of data was reduced to a specific and limited number of general categories. In Table 3, the major categories by source of codes and concepts of the university's social responsibility model are presented, and in Table 4, the major categories by source of codes and concepts of the social entrepreneurship model are presented.

Table 3: Major categories by source of codes and concepts of the social responsibility model of the university

Row	Code	Concepts	Categories
1	F1 F5	Applying the continuous process of innovation, adaptability and learning the necessary processes and structures, taking into account cultural compatibility	adaptability and learning
2	F2	Agents of change in the social sector	Agents of change in the social sector
3	F3 F20 F22 F29 F35	Identification and stubborn encouragement of new opportunities Identifying new opportunities, basic teaching and learning Welcoming new ideas and opinion Assessing the current situation and formulating educational programs according to existing capacities and future needs Identification and stubborn encouragement of new opportunities and agents of change in the social sector	Identifying new opportunities
4	F4	Accepting the mission to create and survive social value	Creation and survival of social value
5	F6	Applying a written evaluation system based on future changes	Applying a written evaluation system

6	F7 F23 F45	Focus on strategic positions Knowing critical and strategic situations in the organization by evaluating the existing conditions and capabilities and drawing the optimal conditions and the priority of strategic needs	Focus on strategic positions
7	F8 F15	Evaluation of existing capabilities and needs assessment of university missions in the future Evaluation of existing capabilities and potentials	Evaluation of existing capabilities
8	F9 F21 F24 F30 F31 F36 F38	Identification and recruitment of capable forces Discovering people's talents and skills instead of qualifications Identifying the capabilities of people and creating a sense of responsibility in them Forming entrepreneurial groups and creating the necessary infrastructure Appropriate needs assessment and selection of people with related capabilities Attention to human potential and available resources and attention to the necessary structures for their optimal use Optimal allocation of resources and efficient human resources	Identification and recruitment of capable forces
9	F10 F26 F41 F42 F44 F46 F47 F48	Economic and organizational incentives to motivate the development of social entrepreneurship Creating incentive mechanisms to encourage people for accepting social responsibility Assessment of existing capabilities and social needs Effective and efficient management of resources with a regional and sector perspective Accepting the mission to create and survive social value Appropriate management based on the attitude of local conditions Creating inter-organizational communication and coordination of all organizations in line with social responsibilities The university's ability to adapt to the conditions in the market and industry and the needs of society	Development of social entrepreneurship
10	F11 F32 F34 F43	Serious and fearless action through available resources Preference for resources within the organization and for additional skills that are not available in the organization for the short term Providing an ambitious sense of accountability to institutions and resulting outcomes and serious and fearless action through available resources Serious and fearless action through available resources	Serious and fearless action through available resources
11	F12	Providing an ambitious sense of accountability to institutions and resulting outcomes	accountability to institutions and resulting outcomes

12	F13 F28	Creating a platform for transformational leadership and reforming processes and structures Improving processes and structures by assigning and equipping practical workshops	Modifying processes and structures
13	F14 F16 F27 F17 F37	Using the written evaluation system and paying attention to the future educational needs of the society Attention to education based on future needs and innovation Need assessment of training courses related to the field of entrepreneurship Assessing needs and using all capacities to provide them Explaining the role of universities in identifying the needs of society and the ways to meet them	Attention to the future educational needs of society
14	F18 F39	Applying new management methods in coordination and compatibility between industry and university University and industry connection	University and industry connection
15	F19	Informing people of the effectiveness and importance of their role in accepting the responsibility of creating change in the social sector	The effectiveness of people in creating change in the social sector
16	F25	Using factors such as organizational incentives	reward system
17	F33 F40	Attention to the role of new technologies that can be used Educational and hardware processes and structures	Using up-to-date technology

Table 4: Major categories by source of codes and concepts of social entrepreneurship model

Row	Code	Concepts	Categories
1	E1 E2	The university rector's belief in entrepreneurship and innovation Encouraging and persuading professors to carry out entrepreneurial activities by the university president	Management attitude to entrepreneurship
2	E3	Appointment of vice presidents with entrepreneurial and innovative attitude and thinking by the university rector	meritocracy and competency-based selection
3	E4 E11 E12 E13	Holding national and annual conferences and meetings by university entrepreneurship centers Editing and preparing a joint publication between the university, industry and entrepreneurs The existence of research centers in the university The existence of university-affiliated research centers	Research activity
4	E14 E9 E17	Reduction of unemployed graduates Employment opportunities for students Hiring specialist staff in the research and development department	Reduce unemployment

5	E5 E21 E15 E16	Establishing permanent secretariats of scientific conferences on the subject of entrepreneurship and innovation at the university level Forming a committee and specialized group of entrepreneurship and innovation in the university Approving research projects with the subject of entrepreneurship, technology and innovation Inclusion of academic entrepreneurship goals in the statement, and missions of the university	Entrepreneurial structures
6	E6 E7	Responsiveness to society Responding to social demand	Social consequences
7	E8	Responding to the labor market	Economic consequences
8	E19 E20 E30 E31	Promoting the culture of entrepreneurship and innovation in the university Formation of university entrepreneurship corridors Creating commitment and attachment to the category of entrepreneurship among faculty members The university rector's commitment to the development of entrepreneurship	Entrepreneurial culture
9	E32 E24 E25 E36	Creating an entrepreneurial atmosphere Applying the spirit of innovation and entrepreneurship in university management and planning Organizational excellence of the university Creating a sense of belonging to entrepreneurship in employees and professors	Organizational Culture
10	E10 E18 E23 E22	Creating competition between entrepreneurial universities Identifying the talents and entrepreneurial abilities of professors Holding development courses for faculty members with a focus on entrepreneurship and technology University membership in professional and international entrepreneurship institutions and associations	Professional development of entrepreneurship
11	E26	Inviting local entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university	Interaction with the local environment
12	E27 E29 E33	Inviting national entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university Communication with work environments and labor market Communicating with justice and establishing rights between university and industry	Interaction with the national environment

13	E28	Inviting international entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university	Interaction with the transnational environment
14	E34 E35	Strengthening collective identity among academic agents Encouraging and encouraging teamwork among academic staff	Participatory Culture

Axial coding: in this stage, the categories are linked together in a network; The macro-categories of characteristics and dimensions of open coding are compiled and put in place to create a knowledge about relationships. Axial coding has three stages; The first stage: creating the main categories. The sub-categories were grouped into 17 main categories in the social responsibility model of the university and 14 main categories in the social entrepreneurship model, as presented in the previous table.

The second stage is to create a communication network between all the categories in a multi-level format. In this stage, one of the open coding categories is selected as the main category or phenomenon (or the studied process) and connects the other categories. The six research categories are as follows. Core categories is an idea, an incident or event that concepts and categories are created on its axis. This is because none of the categories of this research is more abstract than other categories. For the central phenomenon, the name appropriate to the topic of the research has been chosen and it has been placed as a central phenomenon in the heart of other categories in the form of a paradigm model. This table has five main categories and 17 subcategories which are stated in table 5.

Table 5: Key concepts and categories of the research

The main categories of research		
1	Development of social entrepreneurship	Economic and organizational incentives to motivate the development of social entrepreneurship
		Creating incentive mechanisms to encourage people to accept social responsibility
		Assessment of existing capabilities and social needs
		Effective and efficient management of resources with a regional and sector perspective
		Accepting the mission to create and survive social value
		Appropriate management based on the attitude of local conditions
		Creating inter-organizational communication and coordination of all organizations in line with social responsibilities
		The university's ability to adapt to the conditions in the market and industry and the needs of society
2	Modifying processes and structures	Creating a platform for transformational leadership and reforming processes and structures

		Improving processes and structures by allocating and equipping practical workshops
3	The effectiveness of people in creating change in the social sector	Informing people of the effectiveness and importance of their role in accepting the responsibility of creating change in the social sector
4	meritocracy and competency-based selection	Appointment of vice presidents with entrepreneurial and innovative attitude and thinking by the university rector
5	Entrepreneurial culture	Promoting the culture of entrepreneurship and innovation in the university
		Formation of university entrepreneurship corridors
		Creating commitment and attachment to the category of entrepreneurship among faculty members
		The university rector's commitment to the development of entrepreneurship

Causal categories: Four main categories of agents of change in the social sector, applying a written evaluation system, focusing on strategic situations and serious and fearless action by means of available resources have been recognized as causal conditions, whose subcategories are presented in the table 6.

Table 6: Concepts and causal categories of the research

Causal categories of research		
1	Agents of change in the social sector	Agents of change in the social sector
2	Applying the written evaluation system	Applying the written evaluation system based on the future changes
3	Focus on strategic positions	Focus on strategic positions
		Knowing critical and strategic situations in the organization
		Evaluating the existing conditions and capabilities and drawing the optimal conditions with the priority of strategic needs
4	Serious and fearless action through available resources	Serious and fearless action through available resources
		Preference for resources within the organization and for additional skills that are not available in the organization for the short term

Contextual categories of research: It indicates the special conditions in which the phenomenon is located. In this research, eight main categories have been identified as effective environmental conditions as described in Table 7.

Table 7: Concepts and contextual categories of the research

Contextual Categories		
1	The connection between industry and university	Applying new management methods in coordination and compatibility between industry and university
		University and industry connection
2	reward system	Attention to the role of new technologies that can be used
		Using factors such as organizational incentives
3	Using up-to-date technology	Educational and hardware processes and structures
4	Research activity	Holding national and annual conferences and meetings by university entrepreneurship centers
		Editing and preparing a joint publication between the university, industry and entrepreneurs
		The existence of research centers in the university
		The existence of university-affiliated research centers
5	Entrepreneurial structures	Establishing permanent secretariats of scientific conferences on the subject of entrepreneurship and innovation at the university level
		Forming a committee and specialized group of entrepreneurship and innovation in the university
		Approving research projects with the subject of entrepreneurship, technology and innovation
		Inclusion of academic entrepreneurship goals in the statement, and missions of the university
6	Interaction with the local environment	Inviting local entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university
7	Interaction with the national environment	Inviting national entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university
		Communication with work environments and labor market
		Communicating with justice and establishing rights between university and industry
8	Interaction with the transnational environment	Inviting international entrepreneurs to cooperate in the university

Intervening categories of research: It is a broad structural context in which the phenomenon occurs and there are a series of special conditions that affect the strategy. In this research, the main category of management's attitude towards entrepreneurship has been identified as an intervening category as described in Table 8.

Table 8: Concepts and categories of research intervention

Categories Of Intervention		
1	Management attitude to entrepreneurship	The university president's belief in entrepreneurship and innovation
		Encouraging and persuading professors to carry out entrepreneurial activities by the university rector

Strategic categories: It refers to those interactions and actions that actors show in response to their circumstances. In this research, eight main categories of adaptation and learning, assessment of existing capabilities, identification and recruitment of capable forces, attention to the future educational needs of the society, reduction of unemployment, organizational culture, professional development of entrepreneurship and collaborative culture have been identified as described in Table 9.

Table 9: Concepts and strategic categories of research

Strategic Categories		
1	Adaptation and learning	Applying the continuous process of innovation, adaptation and learning
		Necessary processes and structures with cultural compatibility in mind
2	Evaluation of existing capabilities	Evaluation of existing capabilities and needs assessment of university missions in the future
		Evaluation of existing capabilities and potentials
3	Identification and recruitment of capable forces	Discovering people's talents and skills instead of qualifications
		Identifying the capabilities of people and creating a sense of responsibility in them
		Forming entrepreneurial working groups and creating the necessary infrastructure
		Appropriate needs assessment and selection of people with related capabilities
		Attention to human potential and available resources and attention to the necessary structures for their optimal use
		Optimal allocation of resources and efficient human resources
4	Attention to the future educational needs of society	Applying the written evaluation system and paying attention to the future educational needs of the society
		Attention to education based on future needs and innovation
		Need assessment of training courses related to the field of entrepreneurship
		Assessing needs and applying all capacities to provide them
		Explaining the role of universities in identifying the needs of society and the ways to meet them
5	Reduce unemployment	Reduction of unemployed graduates
		Employment opportunities for students
		Hiring specialist staff in the research and development department
6	Organizational Culture	Creating an entrepreneurial atmosphere
		Applying the spirit of innovation and entrepreneurship in university management and planning
		Organizational excellence of the university
		Creating a sense of belonging to entrepreneurship in employees and professors
7		Creating competition between entrepreneurial universities

	Professional development of entrepreneurship	Identifying the talents and entrepreneurial abilities of professors
		Holding development courses for faculty members with a focus on entrepreneurship and technology
		University membership in professional and international entrepreneurship institutions and associations
8	Participatory Culture	Strengthening collective identity among academic agents
		Encouraging and encouraging a team among academic staff

Consequence categories: they are the results of strategies to deal with phenomena or to manage and control phenomena. Five consequence categories have been identified as described in Table 10.

Table 10: Concepts and consequential categories of the research

Consequential Categories		
1	Identifying new opportunities	Identification and stubborn encouragement of new opportunities
		Identifying new opportunities, teaching and learning principles
		Welcoming new ideas and opinions
		Assessing the current situation and formulating educational programs according to existing capacities and future needs
		Identification and stubborn encouragement of new opportunities and agents of change in the social sector
2	Creation and survival of social value	Accepting the mission to create and survive social value
3	Accountability to institutions and resulting consequences	Providing an ambitious sense of accountability to institutions and resulting outcomes
4	Social consequences	Responsiveness to society
		Responding to social demand
5	Economic consequences	Responding to the labor market

The third stage, extracting the research model: In this stage, the major categories are related to each other in the form of a model around the central category. In fact, the drawn model deals with the formal description of the categories. The model of this research is drawn according to the items included in the central and selective coding in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The paradigm model of explaining the social responsibilities of universities with the approach of social entrepreneurship (research findings)

DISCUSSION

The dimensions of social entrepreneurship in Iran's public universities were calculated through the review of theoretical foundations and research literature and interviews with key informants of universities. Interview data were analyzed in three stages of open coding, the first stage, the second stage, and axial coding. In the initial stage of open coding, each extracted concept was placed in a category. In choosing categories, we were looking for categories that fill the conceptual space of concepts as much as possible. For this purpose, we have chosen categories that match the concepts and at the same time saturate more conceptual space. Examining the

data obtained in the first stage of open coding, 36 concepts about social entrepreneurship and 48 concepts about social responsibility were obtained. In the second stage of open coding, similar and common concepts and categories were integrated through constant comparative analysis of data. In this way, relying on the most meaningful and abundant concepts and primary categories, sifting and reducing a large volume of data was done. After the main categories of the research were determined, axial coding was done. In the phase of axial coding, we once again analyzed the constant comparison of the data. In this way, we compared the coded data with each other and made them in the form of categories that fit each other. In this regard, we compared the major categories to the point where we can be sure that each class of categories is separate from each other. Then, the relationship of the categories was examined and based on their nature, they were placed under the title of nuclear category. In other words, major categories around one axis formed a solid network of relationships by entering the nuclear category.

CONCLUSION

How the country is progressing in economic, scientific and competitive fields has become an important national development agenda for governments. Over the past few decades, the increasing demands of the knowledge-based economy and the demand for globalization have caused higher education in many countries around the world to undergo some significant changes. It is often difficult to coordinate and improve strategic research and activities with higher education as one of the key components in the national innovation system. The era of unlimited innovation states that companies, instead of having internal behaviors, exponentially carry out their research activities with the help of various external and external units, including universities, so that innovation can be accessed in a more efficient way. Apart from the traditional academic and research missions, universities are currently under tremendous pressure to achieve economic and social development. Higher education has become more of a social and especially economic development, research and development activities in universities cannot be considered as a purely academic profession. Therefore, structurally, universities need to build an academic entrepreneurship ecosystem in which academic entrepreneurship flourishes. In short, the perception of many countries, especially policy makers, is that a closer interaction and cooperation among the government, industry and academia will lead to sustainable economic growth and increased competition in the scientific economy, where innovation is the key factor of these goals. Becoming an entrepreneurial university is understood as a way to solve problems. An entrepreneurial university understands value, creates value and sends value to internal and external environments. Since the movement towards the third academic generation has a central role in educational developments, it is necessary that the trustees of higher education, understanding this necessity, pay more attention to the development process of entrepreneurial universities.

However, it should be noted that the entrepreneurial university model requires a comprehensive and coherent framework. This framework should be designed and compiled in such a way that covers the different angles of the process, introduces the different components of the entrepreneurial university, shows the importance and contribution of each factor, and provides

a suitable tool for identifying the needs related to the entrepreneurial process. Habibi et al. (2020) investigated the impact of social entrepreneurship orientation on social innovation. The results of this research showed that social entrepreneurship orientation on social innovation, as well as social innovation on innovation in products and innovation in services have a positive and significant effect. Nadali Pourpelki et al. (2019) showed that factors such as potential talents with the subcategories of personal competencies and group competencies, public policies with the subcategories of formalization and the procedures of entrepreneurs and capital- material and spiritual investment with the sub-categories of social capital and financial capital were identified as the underlying factors of the development of social entrepreneurship in higher education. Fazli et al. (2019) showed that social entrepreneurs need to know the challenges and strategic measures in the surrounding environment. Recognizing social challenges makes them able to recognize an important part of their obstacles and introduce them to the environment and society around them and act with cooperation and consensus to solve them.

Zare and Safari Dashtaki (2019) showed that empowering policies as a central phenomenon in interaction with other factors lead to the formation of social entrepreneurship and capacity building, physical and psychological strengthening and supporting laws have a great effect on the formation of empowering policies, which ultimately becomes the basis for the emergence of social entrepreneurship.

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